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INDUSTRIAL COMBINED HEAT AND POWER PLANT REPOWERING PROPOSAL

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Abstract

Industrial combined heat and power plants (CHP) in Middle Europe face the problem of tightening emission limits and decreasing thermal efficiency resulting from their ageing. At the same time, focus and financial support for renovation activities are directed on ageing thermal power plants nowadays, while the need for revamp of industrial CHPs is a less discussed topic generally. To highlight the need for action in this sector a model case study is presented. It showcases an industrial CHP, fueled with heavy fuel oil, producing steam for industrial use and electricity on a condensing-extraction turbine. Several technologies are considered that could augment its actual performance and lead to cleaner heat and power production. Among those, internal combustion engines (ICE) and gas turbines (GT) are the most frequently applied solutions in scientific studies as well in real repowering activities. Both technologies are suitable for industrial use as well. General features and pros and cons of industrial CHP repowering by those technologies are discussed; system balances are set up and resulting improvement of the repowered CHP is obtained.

Introduction

Global climate change highlights our obligation to reduce greenhouse gases emissions. Industrial emissions contribute approximately by 30 to 35 % to total anthropogenic emissions¹, and, amongst them, emissions related to heat and power production play a prominent role². Is it thus of utmost importance to pay attention to this industrial sector.

Several methods can be considered when striving to reduce the carbon footprint of the heat and power production plants^{3,4}: fuel switch to cleaner one^{5,6} or to biomass or biofuel^{7,8}, their complete renovation⁹ or partial repowering¹⁰. Apart from this, optimal planning and operational optimization is commonly a low-cost option^{11,12}. All those methods should be evaluated from several viewpoints: energetic, economic and environmental^{13,14}.

For ageing combined heat and power plants (CHP), reconstruction and renovation is necessary. While large thermal and power plants are in the spotlight of researchers and governments¹⁵, industrial CHP receive much less attention¹⁶. The fundamental method to be considered is partial repowering when a new component is incorporated to the CHP as mentioned above¹⁷. Even though repowering by internal combustion engines (ICE) is a reasonable option¹⁸, heat in hot water is a by-product with only limited value for heavy industry consumers. Repowering by gas turbines (GT) is more feasible, yielding hot flue gas as the only by-product which can further serve for steam production¹⁹. All facts considered; GTs are more suitable for this study's purposes mainly due to the higher overall efficiency potential²⁰.

Study objectives

The aims of this contribution are in particular:

- analyzing the model operation of an ageing combined heat and power plant, combusting mixed petroleum residue, both in winter and in summer
- introducing the GT and ICE technologies and highlighting their particular features in repowering of the ageing CHP
- deciding the more convenient repowering option and quantifying its impact on CHP operation in terms of change in its efficiency, in overall power production and in fuel consumption and in carbon dioxide emissions

CHP unit description

In this section, more detailed description of the original plant model scheme and calculation assumptions are presented. Main equipment is displayed in Figure 1, where streams in gaseous state are depicted in dashed lines, while solid lines represent liquid streams. The main task of this CHP is to produce at least 60 MW of electric

energy and high-, intermediate- and low-pressure (HP, IP, LP) extraction steam in desired amounts for export as well as for own consumption.

The scheme consists of several technological units:

- ECT – extraction-condensing turbine driven by high pressure steam (stream no. 1) produced in steam boiler; besides electricity cogeneration, HP IP and LP extraction steam is produced concurrently for export and for own consumption.
- C – condenser; vapor-liquid mixture (wet steam) from the turbine (stream no. 11), condensates from low temperature water heaters and CHTW (chemically treated water) flow into the condenser. Condenser is operated in broad load range between 20 and 90 t/h of inlet wet steam. Condensate exits after condensation at 30°C and is pumped as feed water to a sequence of three LTWH.
- LTWH – low temperature water heaters (depicted as one in schematics for clarity); each one requires separate extraction steam stream from ECT with the condensation temperature of the inlet steam of 5°C above the temperature of outlet feed water. This way a sufficient heat-exchange driving force is ensured. In each LTWH, the temperature of feed water is increased by 30°C, exiting at 120°C to the degasser.
- CHTW – chemically treated water; while there are a few streams considered as material loss such as blowdown from the boiler, degasser exhaust, even export steam, those need to be replaced.
- DEGASSER – embodies two purposes - feed water degassing and feed water heater; inlet water (stream no. 16) is mixed (into an outlet feed water (stream no. 17) at the temperature of 120°C) with steam from another turbine extraction (stream no. 6a), expander steam, condensates from fuel and air pre-heating and also condensates from HTWH.
- HTWH – high temperature water heater; fulfilling the same role as LTWH with a sequence of two HTWH simplified into one in the scheme.
- BOILER – unit transforming feed water into steam (stream no. 1) at the temperature of 530°C and the pressure of 9 MPa; combustion of pre-heated fuel (stream no. 35, mixed petroleum residue) with air (stream no. 37) takes place resulting in exhaust gas production.

Figure 1. Simplified schematics of CHP unit (with a repowering option in grey). Legend: C = condenser; COMB CH = combustion chamber; COMP = compressor; CHTW = chemically treated water; ECT = extraction-condensing turbine; T = turbine.

Repowering proposals

After we identified the operation conditions of the CHP, the decision-making process concerning altering the CHP unit takes place. The main step of partial repowering is supplementing the original boiler with new heat source fired by natural gas. Choosing a power source in units of up to tens of megawatts, either a combustion gas turbine (GT) or an internal combustion engine (ICE) is used. There are few differences in applications and site performance of both technologies in thermal power plants depending on start-up time, plant repowering cost, power to heat or power to weight ratio etc.

ICE is a machine that produces thermal and electric energy by converting chemical energy contained in fuel into mechanical work of a moving piston²¹, all happening in a very fast start-up time with multiple starts in a day²². This means incorporating ICE with a system of heat exchangers shows promising results during fluctuating load operation throughout the day, especially in peak hours without the efficiency losses occurring under part load operation. Nevertheless, ICE warms up and some components require cooling. For this purpose, cooling water is usually used, and its amount and temperature are often the limiting factor, which is the reason why such solution is more suitable in cases with significant hot water demand. In the analyzed plant, however, there is little use for hot water, as it is steam, not hot water, that is exported from the CHP unit.

In GT, compressed air from its compressor module and fuel are combusted. Flue gas expands through a turbine leaving it at a high temperature²³. High rate of used excess air indicates larger amount of oxygen in flue gas. This offers the possibility of using the flue gas as combustion air mixed with the fresh air in the boiler. Comparing both technologies, the total installed masses of GTs are smaller and there is the benefit from lower equipment weight than with ICEs resulting in higher power to weight ratio²². Moreover, there is almost no cooling water required. On the other hand, unlike ICEs, gas turbines show poor efficiency at low loadings.

All facts considered, option with GT firing natural gas (NG), using flue gas as a combustion air was chosen and the mathematical model was assembled.

Mathematical model

First step is determination of stream enthalpies. The reference state for water and steam is 0°C, 611 Pa, liquid, thus enthalpies are taken from the water tables and graphs. Steam outlets from turbine and superheated steam enthalpies are determined from the h-s diagram of water vapor and from the properties of boiling water and saturated water vapor²⁴. Steam outlets after polytropic expansion and their enthalpy are calculated from equation (1) for isentropic efficiency η_{IS} , where efficiencies of 90 % in superheated and of 80 % in wet steam regions are assumed for the expansion.

$$\eta_{IS} = \frac{h_1 - h_3}{h_1 - h_2} \quad (1)$$

where h_1, h_2 = enthalpies after isentropic expansion, h_3 = enthalpy after polytropic expansion.

Condensate enthalpy is obtained from the tables - Properties of boiling water and saturated water vapour²⁴.

Enthalpy of exhaust gases is calculated using the tables - Molar heat capacity of substances as a function of temperature²⁴. The reference state for air is 0°C, 101,3 kPa, gaseous state and the humid air enthalpies are calculated by equation (2)

$$\bar{h}_{\bar{Y}} = \bar{c}p_G \cdot (T - T_{ref}) + \bar{Y} \cdot (\bar{c}p_W^g \cdot (T - T_{ref})) \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{c}p_G$ = heat capacity of air, T = temperature of humid air, T_{ref} = reference temperature of air (0°C), \bar{Y} = relative mass fraction of water vapor in humid air, $\bar{c}p_W^g$ = heat capacity of water vapor.

Material and enthalpic balances of CHP components, mainly extraction-condensing turbine, low and high temperature water heaters, degasser and boiler were formed. The basic approach is showed in equations (3) and (4)

$$\sum \dot{m}_{in} = \sum \dot{m}_{out} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum h_{in} \dot{m}_{in} = \sum h_{out} \dot{m}_{out} \quad (4)$$

where \dot{m} = mass flow, h = enthalpy, lower index *in* = inlet output, lower index *out* = outlet output.

For comparison purposes, specific indicators for the CHP need to be chosen. The most important ones are mass flow of vapor-liquid mixture to condenser \dot{m}_{11} , mass flow of produced carbon dioxide \dot{m}_{CO_2} in flue gas, the amount of electricity production $P_{el,total}$, which are calculated from the material and enthalpic balances, cogeneration η_{cog} and electric efficiency η_{el} of the power plant, mass flow of inlet steam to ECT \dot{m}_1 , heat flow of exported steam Q_{export} and the amount of produced heat by combusting the fuel Q_{fuel} calculated by a set of following equations.

The electrical efficiency of CHP is the ratio of the amount of produced electricity and the total heat obtained by burning fuel as shown in equation (5):

$$\eta_{el} = \frac{P_{el,total}}{Q_{fuel}} \quad (5)$$

Calculation of cogeneration efficiency in equation (6) represents the amount of heat for export, the heat flowing in with chemically treated water and the amount of electricity produced in relation to the total heat obtained by burning fuel.

$$\eta_{cog} = \frac{P_{el,total} + Q_{exp} - Q_{chtw}}{Q_{fuel}} \quad (6)$$

The individual variables from equations (5) and (6) are calculated as follows, equations (7) to (9):

$$Q_{fuel} = LHV_{NG}\dot{m}_{NG} + LHV_{mazut}\dot{m}_{mazut} \quad (7)$$

where LHV_{NG} = lower heating value of natural gas, \dot{m}_{NG} = mass flow of natural gas, LHV_{mazut} = lower heating value of mixed petroleum residue, \dot{m}_{mazut} = mass flow of mixed petroleum residue.

$$Q_{chtw} = h_{39}\dot{m}_{39} \quad (8)$$

where h_{39} = enthalpy of chemically treated water, \dot{m}_{39} = mass flow of chemically treated water.

$$Q_{exp} = h_3\dot{m}_3 + h_5\dot{m}_5 + h_7\dot{m}_7 \quad (9)$$

where h_3, h_5, h_7 = enthalpies of high-, intermediate- and low-pressure export steam, $\dot{m}_3, \dot{m}_5, \dot{m}_7$ = mass flows of the particular streams for export.

Table I

Steam produced for export

Steam	\dot{m}_{winter} (t/h)	\dot{m}_{summer} (t/h)
high-pressure	60	60
intermediate-pressure	80	80
low-pressure	130	30

The demand for export steam changes depending on the season. Export stream mass flows are listed in Table I. It is assumed that lowered demand for low-pressure steam during summer results in more waste heat production caused by higher mass flow of wet steam to condenser²⁵. The solution is to cut the extra electricity production in summer to 60 MW both from extraction-condensing turbine and gas turbine. On the contrary, the issue in winter is the exact opposite, when higher amount of produced low-pressure steam reduces the production of wet steam, while ECTs design features allow it to operate within a limited range of wet steam flow. A new restriction is introduced, alongside minimum electricity demand of 60 MW, also minimum production of 20 tons of vapor-liquid mixture per hour is required in winter. Results can be observed in Table II.

Table II
Comparison both for existing (E) and repowered (R) CHP

Indicators	Winter (E)	Summer (E)	Winter (R)	Summer (R)
\dot{m}_1 (t/h)	453.7	394.9	453.7	332.6
Q_{fuel} (MW)	333.9	289.7	361.0	249.4
\dot{m}_{11} (t/h)	20	87.2	20	46.7
\dot{m}_{CO_2} (t/h)	92.6	80.6	95.7	71.2
Q_{export} (MW)	222.2	143.1	222.2	143.1
$P_{el,total}$ (MW)	64.3	60	82.1	60
η_{cog} (%)	85.8	70.1	84.3	80.7
η_{el} (%)	19.6	21	23.1	27.8

Model results and discussion

By assembling mathematical model of the CHP in this study, essential understanding of specific technological units functioning was obtained.

Based on the results in Table II, a slight increase in CO₂ production in winter and a small decrease of this indicator in summer can be observed. On the contrary to an ambiguous effect of repowering on carbon dioxide emissions, a substantial decrease in the emissions of other pollutants as a result of partial replacement of mixed petroleum residue by cleaner gaseous fuel combustion, in line with the results of underlying studies^{26,27}.

Furthermore, an increase in electrical efficiency from 19.6 % to 23.1 % in winter and from 21 % to 27.8 % in summer was obtained by calculations. It can be assumed, that this difference is caused by adding a new, more efficient source of electric energy production, while there is only a slight increase in fuel energy input in winter. The observable increase in electric efficiency is in line with the findings of Rokni who performed a study on repowering an obsolete 250 MWe coal-fired power plant by gas turbines and achieved an increase of electric efficiency from the base value of 33 % to around 50 % in full repowering mode²⁸. However, on the contrary to our study, Rokni assumed invasive repowering resulting in an over 100 % increase in total power production of the plant, whereas the repowering in this study yielded only a modest 20 % power production increase. Thus, the impact on electric efficiency of the repowered plant compared to the base design is less pronounced. In summer, the demand for fuel energy input decreases because of lowering the extra electricity production by steam condensation in the condensing turbine, thus lowering the superheated steam production in the boiler.

A decrease of cogeneration efficiency by over 1 % in winter is due to higher fuel energy consumption associated by elevated stack losses, while in summer, the increase of the cogeneration efficiency by almost 10 % occurs. It is worth mentioning that the load of the last expansion stage of the ECT does not fall below the permitted limit of 20 t/h of wet steam.

Conclusion

The aim of this case study was to describe the old thermal power plant functioning with the repowering options evaluation.

In summer, cogeneration and electricity production efficiency appears to be lower. The reason is reduced demand for export steam, which means higher amount of steam expanding in the low-pressure part of the turbine resulting in more waste heat production. This stresses the need to considerate the seasonal impact on CHP operation^{29,30}. Repowering yields an increase of cogeneration efficiency, and, as a result, lower fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions.

According to study conducted in Departments of Mechanical Engineering of various universities in Iran, using GT is an essential repowering method used for energy production improvement and operating lifetime of the unit extension³¹. As the results in Table II show, it is obvious that adding GT to the cycle leads to more efficient electricity production.

This study presents one of the many methods how to balance between the increasing energy production demand and the need for a cleaner environment.

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